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Combined Supercapacitor and Battery Sliding Mode Control for Aeronautic Application

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Abstract—Aircraft electrification is one of the growing trends pushing towards a cleaner aviation. The More Electric Aircraft paradigm, having as objective the replacement of hydraulic/pneumatic actuators with electric ones, represents an intermediate step of this journey. In this work, a battery and a supercapacitor installed on the aircraft power grid are controlled through DC/DC converters in order to reduce the stress on both the mechanical and electric parts of the main aircraft generator. Stability properties of the considered grid are proved and a Second Order Sliding Mode control algorithm is applied for converters control. The effectiveness of the proposed strategy is shown by detailed simulations in Matlab/Simscape/Electronics.

Index Terms—Sliding Mode Control, Aeronautic Application, Power Systems, Robust Control.

I. INTRODUCTION

Guided by the strict necessity to reduce fuel consumption and gas emissions, in the past two decades wide steps have been made towards vehicles electrification. While electric and hybrid cars are currently largely available on the market, the aeronautic sector still needs to overcome many challenges related to battery sizing, weight and aircraft range. As an intermediate step between traditional fuel-powered aircraft and full electric/hybrid propulsion, the idea of the *More Electric Aircraft* (MEA) [1], [2] aims at improving the current aircraft paradigm. In fact, MEA concept is based on the replacement of hydraulic and pneumatic actuators with electric ones. The reason behind such replacement lies in the increased reliability and lower weight that electric actuators can offer when compared with their hydraulic and pneumatic counterparts due to the elimination of heavy pumps and compressor machines and leaky hydraulic systems. Nevertheless, the increased amount of electric devices onboard the MEA recalls for the need of designing advanced strategies for power generation, distribution, conversion and management. As a consequence, many research projects have been and are still currently exploring this topic. For instance, in Europe several Framework Programmes ([3],

[4]) or the more recent initiatives CleanSky and CleanSky2 [5] proposed a large number of projects aimed at investigating the potential of the MEA paradigm.

The classical aeronautic electric power generation and distribution system relies on the so-called High Voltage (HV) side (usually, a 270 VDC bus), powered by an electric generator undergoing a rectification stage. Large loads such as anti-icing, de-icing or cabin pressurization system are directly fed by the HV bus, while conversion stages are purposely designed to connect loads and alternative energy storage devices (such as batteries or supercapacitors) requiring lower voltage to the so-called Low Voltage (LV) side (characterize with a voltage in the range [28, 110]V). The presence of two different voltage levels allows the implementation of advanced power management techniques. For instance, in [6], [7] the presence of an auxiliary LV battery is exploited to enforce an overload management strategy using the energy stored in the auxiliary battery to keep the main generator current below a prescribed threshold during critical phases of the flight and charging the battery during standard scenarios. While the above work only accounts for resistive loads, in [8] authors also consider the case of constant power load. Furthermore, the installation onboard of supercapacitors has been proved to be instrumental to reduce the stress on the mechanical parts of the aeronautic generator. In fact, as showed in [9], [10], supercapacitors can be employed to provide fast current transient required by Electro-Mechanical Actuators (EMAs) during their operations, thus allowing the main generator to provide only the slow transient component to the EMAs. Finally, another possible strategy that has been investigated to avoid the overload of the aircraft generator relies on loads power partial shedding (see [11] and references therein).

The key devices required to put into place the above power management strategies are the power converters (such as buck, boost, buck-boost and others), operating as bridge between the HV side and the LV side. Many approaches have been proposed in the literature to control power converters, starting from linear control algorithms [12] up to more recent approaches based on the framework of hybrid systems [13].

Due to converter parameters uncertainties and measurement noise, robustness is one of the key points when designing con-

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Fig. 1: More Electric Aircraft Power Grid Schematic

control algorithms for DC/DC converters. Sliding Mode Control (SMC) is widely known for its intrinsic robustness against parametric uncertainties. Discontinuous sliding mode control for DC/DC converters control was deeply discussed in [14], where the discontinuous signal generated by first-order Sliding Mode Control is directly applied to the converter switches, avoiding the PWM modulation. Nevertheless, PWM modulation is strictly required for aeronautic applications to ensure finite switching frequency of power converters. Therefore, Higher Order SMC (HOSMC) [15] algorithms result to be good candidates to enforce a continuous control signal, i.e. the duty cycle driving the PWM, while simultaneously inherit the robustness characteristics of discontinuous SMC.

In this work, the above ideas are merged together to enlarge the existing state-of-the-art for power converters control for aeronautic applications. In what follows, the presence of both a supercapacitor and a battery pack onboard the aircraft power grid is exploited to achieve a dual objective: i) let the supercapacitor provide/absorb fast power transients required by the EMAs installed onboard; ii) enforce a load sharing strategy to let the installed battery provide part of the slow transient component of the EMAs. These goals can be achieved through simultaneous control of two DC/DC converters using SubOptimal Second Order SMC (SOSMC) [16]. Moreover, prior to the design of the control algorithm, a stability analysis of the proposed power grid has been performed.

II. MORE ELECTRIC AIRCRAFT POWER GRID

The MEA power grid can be schematically represented as in Figure 1 where, from left to right, E_{gen} represents the 270V main voltage generator installed on-board with internal resistance R_{gen} . The main generator is physically connected to the rest of the grid through cable lines with inductance L_{bus} . The EMA is here modeled as a time varying current source absorbing a given current $I_{ema}(t)$. Two bidirectional converters are then connected to the grid: one consisting of

resistances R_{c_1} , R_{l_1} , capacitor C_1 , inductor L_1 and switches S_1 – S_2 , and one consisting of resistances R_{c_2} , R_{l_2} , capacitor C_2 , inductor L_2 and switches S_3 – S_4 . The former converter is connected to a supercapacitor indicated with C_{sc} characterized by inner resistance R_{sc} , while the latter bridges the HV bus with a LV battery indicated with E_{bat} . Considering the four possible configurations of the switches positions, it is possible to retrieve the set of differential equations describing the dynamic behaviour of the entire power grid:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \dot{x}_1 &= \frac{1}{L_{bus}R_c} [- (R_{gen}R_c + R_{c_1}R_{c_2}) x_1 - R_{c_2}x_2 \\
 &\quad - R_{c_1}x_5 + R_cE_{gen} + R_{c_1}R_{c_2}I_{ema}(t)] \\
 \dot{x}_2 &= \frac{1}{C_1R_c} [-x_2 + x_5 - R_c x_3 u_1 + R_{c_2}x_1 - R_{c_2}I_{ema}(t)] \\
 \dot{x}_3 &= \frac{1}{L_1} [-R_{l_1}x_3 - x_4 + x_2 u_1] \\
 \dot{x}_4 &= \frac{1}{C_{sc}} \left[-\frac{1}{R_{sc}} x_4 + x_3 \right] \\
 \dot{x}_5 &= \frac{1}{C_2R_c} [-x_5 + x_2 - R_c x_6 u_2 + R_{c_1}x_1 - R_{c_1}I_{ema}(t)] \\
 \dot{x}_6 &= \frac{1}{L_2} [-R_{l_2}x_6 + x_5 u_2 - E_{bat}]
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where x_1 is the bus current, x_2 and x_5 represent the input voltage of the first and second converter, respectively, x_3 and x_6 indicate the output current of the first and second converter, respectively, and x_4 indicates the supercapacitor voltage. Furthermore, $u_1 \in \{0, 1\}$ represents the position of the switches S_1 – S_2 , while $u_2 \in \{0, 1\}$ indicates the configuration of switches S_3 – S_4 . Finally, in what follows we indicate with I_1 , I_2 the input currents for the two converters and, for the sake of notation brevity, we define $R_c = R_{c_1} + R_{c_2}$.

III. STABILITY ANALYSIS & CONTROL DESIGN

A. Stability Properties of the System

Prior to defining the converters control laws, it is of interest to investigate the stability properties of system (1).

Lemma 1. *System (1) is stable in the Lyapunov sense.*

Proof. The proof follows similar arguments as in [17, Lemma 1]. System (1) can be represented as a linear switched system of the form

$$\dot{x} = A_i x + b, \quad (2)$$

where matrices A_i with $i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, indicates the possible value of the dynamic matrix of system (1) for the switches configurations (u_1, u_2) , i.e. $\{(0, 0), (1, 0), (0, 1), (1, 1)\}$ and b contains the forcing terms related to E_{gen} , E_{bat} and I_{ema} .

It can be easily proved that the Lyapunov function candidate

$$V = \frac{1}{2} [L_{bus}x_1^2 + C_1x_2^2 + L_1x_3^2 + C_{sc}x_4^2 + C_2x_5^2 + L_2x_6^2],$$

is a common Lyapunov function [18] for the unforced version of system (2). In fact, its time derivative is

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V} = & - \left(R_{gen} + \frac{R_{c1}R_{c2}}{R_c} \right) x_1^2 - \frac{1}{R_c}(x_2 - x_5)^2 - R_{l2}x_3^2 \\ & - \frac{1}{R_{sc}}x_4^2 - R_{l2}x_6^2, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

for all $i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$. Note that this function is only negative semi-definite, thus proving the statement by virtue of [19, Theorem 4.1]. \square

The importance of the result presented in Lemma 1 is dual: firstly, it is proved that the state of system (1) cannot grow unbounded, which in turn implies that there exist negative scalars X_1^-, X_3^- and X_6^- , and positive scalars $X_1^+, X_2^-, X_2^+, X_3^+, X_4^-, X_4^+, X_5^-, X_5^+$ and X_6^+ such that $x_1 \in [X_1^-, X_1^+]$, $x_2 \in [X_2^-, X_2^+]$, $x_3 \in [X_3^-, X_3^+]$, $x_4 \in [X_4^-, X_4^+]$, $x_5 \in [X_5^-, X_5^+]$ and $x_6 \in [X_6^-, X_6^+]$. It must be noted that, in general, Lyapunov analysis presented in Lemma 1 does not indicate the sign of the bounds of the state. Nevertheless, considering that states x_2 , x_4 and x_5 represent capacitors voltages, it can be safely assumed that they belong to positive intervals. Secondly, proof of boundedness of the system state uniformly with any choice of control inputs u_1 and u_2 , allows the design of the control algorithm to be mainly focused on the closed-loop system performance rather than the stability of the residual dynamics, as it will be detailed in the following.

B. Control Design

The converters of in the power grid in Figure 1 are required to be controlled in order to achieved two concurrent goals:

- exploit the presence of the supercapacitor to smoothen the generator current when the EMA requires a piece-wise varying current;
- use the energy stored in the battery to provide the slow component of the power required by the EMA.

These two control objectives require the regulation of currents I_1 and I_2 to appropriate set points, \bar{I}_1 and \bar{I}_2 ,

respectively. Relying on power balance across input and output sections of both converters, the control objectives can be translated as the selection of two sliding functions chosen as

$$\sigma_1(x, t) = x_3(t)x_4(t) - x_2(t)\bar{I}_1(t), \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_2(x, t) = E_{bat}x_6(t) - x_5(t)\bar{I}_2(t). \quad (5)$$

In order to detect the fast component of the EMA current profile, the reference signal $\bar{I}_1(t)$ can be generated by filtering the EMA current through a high-pass filter as

$$\bar{I}_1(t) = D(t) * I_{EMA}(t), \quad (6)$$

where the operator $*$ denotes the convolution, and $D(t)$ is the impulse response of the filter. On the other hand, the slow component of the EMA current profile can be detected through a low pass filter applied to the EMA profile. Thus, the reference $\bar{I}_2(t)$ is generated as

$$\bar{I}_2(t) = G(t) * I_{EMA}(t), \quad (7)$$

where $G(t)$ is the low pass filter.

Regarding the design of the control laws for input u_1 and u_2 , it can be noted that the sliding variables (4) and (5) have relative degree (i.e., the minimum order r of the time derivative $\sigma^{(r)}$ in which the control u explicitly appears) equal to one with respect to u_1 and u_2 , respectively. This in turn implies that a first order sliding mode control could in theory be applied to steer the currents I_1 and I_2 to their references $\bar{I}_1(t)$ and $\bar{I}_2(t)$. However, in practical applications, switches of power converters are regulated through PWM modulators, which require continuous duty cycle as input. This requirement makes application of first order sliding mode control unfeasible with PWM modulation due to its discontinuous nature. A possible solution to obtain a continuous control input while preserving the properties of SMC consists in resorting to HOSMC. Specifically, this approach is based on artificially increasing the relative degree of the system to obtain an augmented order system with an integral dynamics and relative degree one with respect to the input derivative.

Denoting $\sigma_1(t) = \zeta_1(t)$, the augmented order system for the sliding variable (4) is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\zeta}_1(t) &= \zeta_2(t), \\ \dot{\zeta}_2(t) &= f_1(x, u_1, t) + g_1(x, t)v_1, \\ \dot{u}_1(t) &= v_1, \\ \dot{z}_1(t) &= h_1(z_1, x, t), \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(x, u_1, t) &= \frac{x_4}{L_1}(-R_{l1}\dot{x}_3 - \dot{x}_4 + \dot{x}_2u_1) + \frac{x_3}{C_{sc}}\left(-\frac{\dot{x}_4}{R_{sc}} + \dot{x}_3\right) \\ & - \frac{\bar{I}_1}{C_1R_c}\left(-\dot{x}_2 + \dot{x}_5 - R_c\dot{x}_3u_1 + R_{c2}(\dot{x}_1 - \dot{I}_{ema})\right) \\ & + 2(\dot{x}_3\dot{x}_4 - \dot{x}_2\dot{I}_1) - x_2\ddot{I}_1, \\ g_1(x, t) &= \frac{x_2x_4}{L_1} + \frac{x_3\bar{I}_1}{C_1}, \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 2: MATLAB Simulink Simscape/Electronics Simulation Model

are uncertain vector fields that can be proved to be bounded by virtue of the results from the stability analysis of the Lemma 1. Hence, there exist positive scalars F_1 , G_{1m} and G_{1M} such that

$$\begin{aligned} |f_1(x, u_1, t)| &\leq F_1 \quad \forall(x, u_1, t) \in \mathbb{R}^6 \times [0, 1] \times \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}, \\ 0 < G_{1m} &\leq g_1(x, t) \leq G_{1M} \quad \forall(x, t) \in \mathbb{R}^6 \times \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}. \end{aligned}$$

The last line in (8) represents the so-called internal dynamics.

Similarly, with regards to the sliding variable (5), denoting $\sigma_2(t) = \xi_1(t)$, the augmented order system is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\xi}_1(t) &= \xi_2(t), \\ \dot{\xi}_2(t) &= f_2(x, u_2, t) + g_2(x, t)v_2, \\ \dot{u}_2(t) &= v_2, \\ \dot{z}_2(t) &= h_2(z_2, x, t), \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} f_2(x, u_2, t) &= \frac{E_{bat}}{L_2} (-R_{l_2} \dot{x}_6 + \dot{x}_5 u_2 - \dot{E}_{bat}) \\ &\quad - \frac{\bar{I}_2}{C_2 R_c} (-\dot{x}_5 + \dot{x}_2 - R_c \dot{x}_6 u_2 + R_{c_1} (\dot{x}_1 - \dot{I}_{ema})) \\ &\quad + 2(\dot{E}_{bat} \dot{x}_6 - \dot{x}_5 \dot{I}_2) + \ddot{E}_{bat} x_6, \\ g_2(x, t) &= \frac{E_{bat} x_5}{L_2} + \frac{x_5 x_6}{C_2}, \end{aligned}$$

are uncertain vector fields that bounded by positive scalars F_2 , G_{2m} and G_{2M} as

$$\begin{aligned} |f_2(x, u_2, t)| &\leq F_2 \quad \forall(x, u_2, t) \in \mathbb{R}^6 \times [0, 1] \times \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}, \\ 0 < G_{2m} &\leq g_2(x, t) \leq G_{2M} \quad \forall(x, t) \in \mathbb{R}^6 \times \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}. \end{aligned}$$

As in system (8), the last equation in (9) represents the internal dynamics for system (9).

Then, for control variables u_1 and u_2 , let $\alpha_i^* \in (0, 1] \cap (0, 3G_{im}/G_{iM})$, $i \in \{1, 2\}$ and

$$\alpha_i = \begin{cases} \alpha_i^* & \text{if } (\sigma_i(x, t) - 0.5\sigma_{iM})(\sigma_{iM} - \sigma_i(x, t)) \\ 1 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where σ_{iM} is the last extremal value of $\sigma_1(x, t)$, and

$$W_i > \max \left(\frac{F_i}{\alpha_i^* G_{im}}; \frac{4F_i}{3G_{im} - \alpha_i^* G_{iM}} \right). \quad (11)$$

Then, in [16] it is proved that the control law

$$v_i(t) = -\alpha_i W_i \text{sign}(\sigma_i(x, t) - 0.5\sigma_{iM}), \quad i \in \{1, 2\}, \quad (12)$$

makes the sliding variables σ_1 , σ_2 converge towards zero in finite time. Furthermore, once the sliding variables converge to zero, convergence analysis of the internal dynamics z_1 , z_2 should be performed. Nevertheless, the stability result of Lemma 1 guarantees that the internal dynamics will remain stable even after convergence of the sliding variables.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

The proposed SOSM control for generator peaks smoothing and load sharing have been tested in a detailed MATLAB/Simulink/Simscape/Electronics simulator, shown in Figure 2 and composed of following blocks:

- EMA: implements the EMA as a controlled current source (yellow block).
- Converter 1 and Converter 2: implement the supercapacitor and the battery converters (orange blocks).
- Battery: emulates the battery storage device (cyan block).
- SOSM Controller: contains the SOSM controller as presented in Section III-B (green block);
- PWM Modulator: contains the modulator that implements the switching logic (grey block).
- Oscilloscopes: allows the visualization of grid currents and voltages (magenta block).

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
E_{gen}	270 [V]	C_2	50 [μ F]
E_{bat}	110 [V]	C_{SC}	7.95 [F]
L_1	2 [mH]	R_{L_1}	89.2 [m Ω]
L_2	2 [mH]	R_{L_2}	10 [m Ω]
L_{bus}	2.4 [μ H]	R_{C_1}	89.2 [m Ω]
C_1	50 [μ F]	R_{C_2}	10 [m Ω]

TABLE I: System Parameters

The power grid parameters are shown in Table I. The simulation has been designed using a realistic EMA current profile shown in Fig. 3 (blue line), which is characterized by rather sharp profile variations. The filters $D(t)$ and $G(t)$ required to generate the current references as in (6) and (7) have been selected as

$$D(s) = \frac{\tau s}{\tau s + 1}, \quad G(s) = \gamma \frac{1}{\tau s + 1}, \quad (13)$$

where $\gamma \in [0, 1]$ represent the power share that we would like the battery to provide to the EMA. In the present case, 50%

Fig. 3: Current profile requested by the EMA (blue line) and current profile provided by the aircraft generator (red line)

of the power requested by the EMA will be provided by the battery (in steady state), i.e. $\gamma = 0.5$.

The red line in Fig. 3 shows the benefits of the controller action: the generator current is much smoother than the EMA requested current due to the supercapacitor action (see Fig. 4). Furthermore, as expected, the battery provides 50% of the EMA current in steady state (see Fig. 5). Finally, Fig. 4 and 5 show the rather good performance of the SOSM control algorithms presented in Section III-B that guarantee finite time attraction of the sliding surface and robustness against variation of the reference signal.

Fig. 4: Current contribution from the supercapacitor (blue line) and generated reference $\bar{I}_1(t)$ (red line).

Fig. 5: Current contribution from the battery (blue line) and generated reference $\bar{I}_2(t)$ (red line).

V. CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE RESEARCH

In this work one of the challenges of the MEA framework has been investigated. The combined control of supercapacitor and battery for generator power smoothing and load share has been tackled through the adoption of a Second Order Sliding Mode control algorithm. Such control technique has been proven to be rather efficient to achieve the control objective. Future research will deal with experimental application of the proposed control strategy taking into account stochastic noise and time delay [20] and investigation towards supervisory control of multiple energy storage device systems.

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